

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: SOUTH AFRICA

Missing: South Africa's Ability to Manage its Reservoir Lakes

**Bill Harding, PhD (Limnology), PhD (Public Law)
Pr Sci Nat.
DH Environmental Consulting (Pty) Ltd
Somerset West, South Africa
Email: bill@dhec.co.za**

One of the most common statements made about South Africa is that it is a country not blessed with an abundance of water. Our climate is arid, with an average annual rainfall of 450 mm that is both unevenly distributed and subject to high levels of evaporation. South Africa boasts a single natural fluvial lake and coastal lake systems are generally unsuitable for raw potable water supply. Hence, the social and economic well-being of South Africa's 62 million people is dependent on water stored in reservoirs, as well as a not-insubstantial reliance on groundwater. However, annual return flows of wastewater effluents are twice the volume provided by groundwater – and it is this substantial component of the annual water balance which continues to threaten the quality of both freshwater and coastal zone resources. Ominously, failed sewerage infrastructure has resulted in significant volumes of raw sewage never reaching treatment works, this apart from the fact that the majority of treatment works are dysfunctional. The environmental impact is thus substantial.

South Africa has 586 man-made lakes, storing thirty-two billion litres of water or 66% of the Mean Annual Runoff (MAR). As much as 76% of the total storage has impaired water quality as a result of elevated nutrient levels – largely originating from the aforementioned inadequately-treated sewage effluents. Outdated concentration-based standards have yet to be replaced by an assimilable loads approach. It is common understanding in South Africa that wastewater effluent treatment is in a very dire state, with eutrophication acknowledged as the primary threat to water quality and the health of the nation's reservoirs and, by extension its population. Cyanobacterial blooms and cyanotoxins are common (Fig. 1), as are vast swathes of floating invasives such as water hyacinth (Fig. 2).

From the above brief background, it might be reasonably assumed that South Africa possesses a cohesive, well-developed and academically-supported national programme for reservoir management. It may, then, come as a shock to learn that South Africa has no such programme, none of our academic institutions teach reservoir limnology as a career subject and the Department of Water and Sanitation ('Department'), the custodian of our water resources, has no Directorate of Reservoir Management that coordinates appropriate stewardship of our dams. The Department does not have a single reservoir limnologist in its employ. Curiously, the National Aquatic Ecosystem Health Monitoring Programme does not mention the terms "reservoir" or "dam"! Sadly, but not inexplicably, reservoir limnology remains the Cinderella of South African aquatic sciences.

So how did this egregious situation arise? Human and economic investment in South African limnology experienced a significant decline towards the end of the 1980s – especially with respect to attention to the science and management of reservoir lakes. This was, in part, underpinned by inaction on the part of the Department and its somewhat startling perception that eutrophication was not a priority issue! A review of the North American literature of the time might have suggested, however ill-advisedly, that eutrophication was considered to be "resolved," largely through legislative initiatives and engineering solutions applied to municipal wastewater

Fig. 1 Cyanobacterial blooms in Hartbeespoort Dam: a) shoreline, b) embayment and c) river inlet (photos by Bill Harding).

treatment. Emphasis was shifting to more exotic contaminants and nonpoint sources. Nevertheless, point-source eutrophication in the so-called 'developing countries' remained, and still remains, a concern, although the costs of applying the developed science are probably too high for these economies to bear.

In South Africa, reports which revealed major problems, and also solutions, were kept confidential – not only by the responsible agency but also by almost the entire cohort of aquatic scientists active at the time. If one was to seek an incentive for this then the conclusion drawn by the late Bill Williams speaks volumes "Denial [of the findings] will certainly result in short-term economic gain; just as certainly, denial will result in considerable long-term disbenefits". South Africa is now reaping the harvest of sustained denial.

The years following 1990 saw increased diversion of funding into river biology and ecology – almost to the exclusion of anything else in aquatic science (except perhaps ecotoxicology). Oddly, despite the interruption of all but one major South African river by dams, there were no calls from the growing fraternity of river ecologists for the authorities to hasten integrated attention to the reservoirs. There was also a myopic focus on water quantity – without due consideration of the ecosystems that are man-made. This led to a perception, especially in the hinterland, that the reservoirs were simply acting as a form of oxidation pond, a view first uttered in 1958!

Organizational changes which prevailed during the 1980s also

Fig. 2 Water hyacinth invasion in Hartbeespoort Dam and b) struggling to reach the shoreline (photos by John Wesson).

contributed to the termination of state-funded reservoir research – just at the time when the country had built a world-renowned team of reservoir limnologists at the National Institute for Water Research (NIWR). The subsequent years saw most of this group move to other careers or countries. Profit-driven government consulting required many highly-skilled specialists to “retrain” into other fields if they wanted to continue earning a living. Few chose to do so and, in one famous case, a world-renowned algologist dumped his life’s work in the garbage rather than retool himself in ‘waste management.’

A limited amount of applied lake management, research and monitoring was undertaken by the larger municipalities and Water Boards – generating a mass of unpublished reservoir-lake data. The bulk of this work was born of a need for the water utilities to understand and manage the nature of the water resources being treated and supplied to consumers. The need for effective early-warning protocols for cyanobacterial blooms is a case in point. One example of these efforts was the establishment of a dedicated cyanotoxin laboratory, the only one in Africa, by the City of Cape Town. However, the bulk of the smaller water providers were left completely unsupported.

Negligible funding was made available for reservoir studies after 1990. An examination of Water Research Commission projects shows that up until 2015 a mere ZAR10 Million (~USD 1 million) was spent on six projects, this being both a fraction of the Commission’s overall budget in general, or that applied to river and wetland science in particular.

South African reservoir limnology science reached its zenith during the 1980s, summarised in the Hartbeespoort Dam Ecosystem Programme Report. The 8-year project generated an international level of impact, 97 publications, 4 PhD’s and a documentary film. Contrastingly, it reached an all-time nadir between 2006 and 2013 in an 8-year attempt to remediate conditions in the notoriously hypertrophic Hartbeespoort Dam, a project that lacked scientific rigour and technical guidance, ignored the fundamental casual issues and prior studies, deliberately ignored skills and advice, generated spurious claims and, instead, wasted ZAR158 Million on cosmetic pseudo-science ‘solutions’, applied by insufficiently qualified or experienced personnel. After eight years not a single publication in a recognised journal had been produced. The project was eventually quietly terminated but, at time of writing, a ‘Hartbeespoort Season 2’ attempt appears to be in the planning stages – absent any indications that lessons were learnt from the previous fiasco.

The inability to attract young South African biological scientists to the field of limnology, especially reservoir limnology, is an enduring constraint to progress. As long as the discipline does not form part of any nationally-acknowledged need, no curricula or career opportunities will open up. Limnology is not a “sexy” science. Unlike chemistry and microbiology, where funds and publication opportunities abound, lake biologists may not become financially-rich but certainly have a unique opportunity for a richly-rewarding outdoor life. Convincing newcomers is difficult, however, if there are no careers for them!

“South African limnology is in disarray. It is poorly-funded, failing to address certain important environmental problems, lacks a cohesive

sense of direction and its potential contributions to effective water resource management are grossly underrated”. This statement is, in several ways, almost as true now in 2023 as it was back in 1989 when it was made by one of the world’s most eminent limnologists, the late Dr Bill Williams. He continued, “Additionally, many of its [South Africa’s] practitioners are dispirited and disillusioned, there has been significant attrition from their ranks, and few young South Africans regard limnology as a secure and attractive career. All of this might be comprehensible in a country with plentiful water of good quality; for this to be the case in a country wherein water is a basic resource and is in short supply, faced with demographic problems of the magnitude prevailing, seems incomprehensible”.

South Africa lacks human resources skilled in reservoir limnology. The few of us that are left can only despair at the mind-boggling recalcitrance to redress this paucity. The failure by the state to recognise and prioritise the environmental health of its man-made lakes has created a scenario in which no training or career opportunities exist for an urgently-needed cohort of reservoir limnologists. It will take decades to mitigate the harm resulting from the failure to have regard for reservoirs as semi-natural water resource ecosystems, this assuming that the economy can bear the now gargantuan cost.

Sources

- Allanson BR, Hart RC, O’Keefe JH, Roberts RD. 1990. Inland waters of southern Africa: An ecological perspective. Monographs in Biology 64. Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 458 pp.
- Harding WR. 2015. Living with eutrophication in South Africa: a review of realities and challenges. Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa. 70: 155-171.
- Mitchell SA, Crafford JG. 2016. Review of the Hartbeespoort Dam Integrated Biological Remediation Programme (Harties Metsi a Me). Water Research Commission Report No. KV 357/16, 256 pp. ISBN 978-1-4312-0803-6.
- Williams WD. 1989. A Statement on the Inland Water Ecosystems Programme and the Current State of Limnology in South Africa. Foundation for Research Development, CSIR, Pretoria.
- Zohary T, Jarvis AC, Chutter FM, Ashton PJ, Roberts R. 1988. The Hartbeespoort Dam ecosystem programme - 1980-1988. Division of Water Technology Report, CSIR, Pretoria. 8pp.

Bill Harding has PhDs in Limnology and Public Law. He has been involved with reservoir-lake science and management since 1988. His first reservoir limnology experience was as a student at Hartbeespoort Dam in 1975. He heads up an amicus group that will observe the current round of remediation efforts. Anyone wishing to be part of this oversight initiative is welcome to contact Bill at bill@dhec.co.za.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10324419>